

“Plastic Waste Management in Bangladesh – A legal analysis”

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ABSTRACT:

In the previous few decades, plastic waste management issues in Bangladesh have become increasingly severe. Development efforts in Bangladesh are hampered by a lack of training in plastic waste management procedures, high population growth rates, and increased commercial activity in metropolitan areas.

In Bangladesh, urban residential areas generate significantly more waste per capita than rural residential areas. The capacity of the nation to efficiently process, dispose of, and recycle plastic waste is severely constrained. Bangladesh, like many other nations, has experienced a major increase in environmental dangers. Many industrialized and developing nations have previously taken various measures for the proper disposal of plastic garbage, however, Bangladesh has not yet taken any significant measures to address this issue. Bangladesh has laws like Jute Packaging Act 2010, Environment Protection Act, 1995 etc. to reduce and manage waste emissions, but these laws are not being utilized properly. This report attempts to analyze and evaluate the effectiveness of Bangladesh's current legal framework for the management of plastic waste.

Keywords: Plastic waste, Bangladesh, plastic garbage, authority, management, toxicological, Government.

Introduction:

Bangladesh is ranked 10th, even though it was the first country to ban poly shopping bags in 2001. The country's low ranking is due to the widespread use of single-use plastics, poor management of these plastics in some areas, and poorly managed landfills that don't have waste separation procedures because of lax laws. (Mercy Tembon June, 2021)¹

Currently, the product created from plastic has become a vital commodity for numerous applications. A vast quantity of discarded plastic creates environmental concerns that endanger marine life, lowers soil fertility, and contaminates ground water. Managing this massive amount of plastic waste is particularly difficult for poorer nations like Bangladesh. Most of the problems with waste management in Bangladesh are caused by a lack of facilities, slow progress on building infrastructure, and a small budget. In this study, the path of plastic waste production in Bangladesh and the current plastic waste management system have been

¹ <https://blogs.worldbank.org/endpovertyinsouthasia/tackling-plastic-pollution-green-growth-bangladesh>

examined in depth. The plastic management system does not appear to incorporate any technical or advanced procedures. A method for the sustainable management of plastics has been developed alongside the obstacles that would arise during their implementation. If the proposed technologies work, they would improve the way plastic waste is resolved in Bangladesh and make a huge amount of energy from waste.

Major Plastic Waste Generator in Bangladesh:

The global manufacturing of plastic has risen during the previous five decades. Every minute, 1 million plastic bottles are bought around the world. If you stacked all the plastic bottles that were sold in 2018, they would be taller than the Burj Khalifa in Dubai, which is the tallest building in the world. (Mahmudul Islam September, 2019)²

A plastic bottle has numerous advantages, but the rising usage of plastic has a terrible impact on the environment.

Bangladesh does not lack plastic risks. Bangladesh continues to be one of the most plastic-polluting nations due to the rising usage of plastics in many industries, especially packaging. Images of rivers choked with plastic bottles due to careless disposal illustrate in part the depth of the problem.

In general, plastic garbage is divided into two categories: hard and soft. Soft plastics are often one-use materials with no value after a single application. Annually, approximately 17,000 tons of soft plastics are disposed of in landfills alongside other kitchen garbage. After a single usage, recyclable hard plastics are sent to factories by various sellers or thrift collectors. afterwards exported as flakes and repurposed for other use.(Md. Niruzzaman, January 2022)³

Bangladesh has some shocking facts regarding plastics:

1. Every day, 3000 tons of plastic garbage are generated.
2. Each year, 8% of all waste generated is plastic. The quantity is 800,000 tons.
3. Every day, around 14 million polythene bags are used in the metropolis of Dhaka. They frequently end up in rivers and oceans, endangering marine life.

² <https://www.tbsnews.net/environment/bangladesh-drowns-8-lakh-tones-plastic-waste-year>

³ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357969147_Plastic_Waste_Governance_in_Bangladesh#pf6

4. Every day, around 73,000 tons of plastic debris enter the ocean via the Padma, Yamuna, and Meghna rivers.
5. About 250 tons of objects that can't be recycled, like plastic straws and silverware, are sold in Old Dhaka alone every month.
6. The creation of bio trash increased by 5.2%, while plastic garbage increased by 7.5%.
7. Plastic trash from India, Nepal, and China flows down the Ganges, Yamuna, and Brahmaputra rivers and ends up in our rivers, canals, and other bodies of water. The bigger the problem, the more it needs to be fixed.

According to Reuters, Asia is the largest producer of plastic and plastic garbage in the world. (Mahmudul Islam, September 2019)⁴

Damage to the Environment, Marine-Life and Humans:

The Environment: Plastics are damaging to the environment. Plastic waste creates an unhygienic atmosphere. These inadequate circumstances breed insects and mosquitoes that transmit malaria and dengue. Each year, we produce 100 million tons of plastic waste, according to the United Nations Environment Program. Given that it takes decades or centuries for plastic garbage to disintegrate, it can be detrimental to the environment if there is an excessive amount. They impair soil fertility or quality, hence hindering plant and tree growth. (Charlie, December 2022)⁵

Plastic contaminates land and water, harms wildlife, and modifies the ecosystem. Plastic pollution is significant. Numerous goods, including plastic bags, bottles, packaging, and toys, are not biodegradable. Plastics that interact with soil inhibit soil's permeability and water flow. The fertility of the soil suffers. Plastic in the ocean has negative effects on wildlife and coral reefs. Plastic wastes kills numerous species. Today, fish and birds consume plastic. They are ruining the environment.

The Marine-Life: Eight million tons of plastic are dumped into the ocean every year from land, sewers, rivers, and other waterways. That is equivalent to placing five trash bags on every foot of the world's shoreline. Plastic does not vanish from the ocean. Instead, it degrades into "microplastics" that are difficult to remove from water. Marine organisms that swallow microplastics may experience starvation or

⁴ <https://www.tbsnews.net/environment/bangladesh-drowns-8-lakh-tones-plastic-waste-year>

⁵ <https://paidforarticles.com/what-damage-does-plastic-cause-to-the-environment-698532>

internal damage. Plastic waste can have negative effects on marine life and human health.

According to scientists, 12 percent of all plastic that enters the water sinks. This may not seem like much, yet it can disrupt the ecosystems of the deep sea. Plastic that sinks can affect marine ecosystems. It can also be consumed by bottom-dwelling animals, who have the same health concerns as surface-dwelling ones.

In the Mariana Trench, marine life consumes more plastic than humans can comprehend. More than 70% of the examined amphipods contained plastic. Together, microplastics and microplastics float.

There are PCBs, BPA, and phthalates in plastic. Plastics in the food chain have a negative impact on indigenous cultures. Ocean plastic waste may be the largest in the planet.

Plastic has poisoned the seas for years. For years, it has grown faster than most media. Each year, 8 to 10 million metric tons of plastic are dumped into the ocean due to marine pollution. The oceans are 80% contaminated by plastic. According to a study, plastics will certainly outweigh aquatic life by 2050. The global plastic output is unaffected by the magnitude of this crisis. The waters are threatened. Plastic pollutes the environment and kills marine life. (Gilad, December 2022).⁶

The Humans:

1. Extraction and Transport

Large quantities of toxic substances are regularly released into the environment during oil and gas production, especially during hydraulic fracturing for natural gas. The production of the primary feedstocks for plastic uses 170 fracturing chemicals, some of which are known to have negative effects on human health. These effects include cancer, neurological, reproductive, and developmental toxicity, immune system deterioration, and more. These toxins have known negative effects on the liver, brain, respiratory, neurological, and gastrointestinal systems as well as the skin, eyes, and other sensory organs.

2. Refining and Manufacture

People living near oil refineries and chemical plants are at risk of exposure to harmful chemicals that can cause cancer, reproductive and developmental disorders,

⁶ <https://planetlovelife.com/the-dangers-of-plastic-pollution-to-marine-life-and-humans/>

and genetic influences like low birth weight. Industry personnel and communities adjacent to refining facilities experience both chronic and acute exposures during uncontrolled discharges and emergency situations.

3. Consumer Goods and Their Packaging

Microplastic particles and hundreds of toxic compounds with known or suspected carcinogenic, developmental, or endocrine-disrupting effects are inhaled and/or ingested when plastic products are used. (Sujata Birla Hospital & Medical Research Center, May 2022)⁷

4. Waste Management

All methods of treating plastic waste result in the release of poisonous materials into the air, water, and soil, including hazardous metals like lead and mercury, organic compounds (dioxins and furans), acid gases, and other toxic substances. As they accumulate in plant and animal tissues, toxins from emissions, fly ash, and slag in a fire pile can travel large distances, deposit in soil, and eventually infiltrate human systems. (James Gaunt on November, 2021)⁸

5. The Effects of Plastic on the Environment

As macro- or microplastics, plastics pollute agricultural soils, terrestrial and aquatic food systems, and water supplies. Toxins already present in the environment can be concentrated or easily absorbed by this environmental plastic, making them once again available for direct or indirect human exposure. When microplastics are eaten or breathed in, they can cause inflammation, genotoxicity, oxidative stress, apoptosis, and necrosis. These effects are linked to a number of bad health outcomes, such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, inflammatory bowel disease, diabetes, rheumatoid arthritis, chronic inflammation, auto-immune conditions, neurodegenerative diseases, and stroke. (CIEL-Center of for International Environmental Law report, 2022)⁹

Existing Waste Management Statutes and Policies Include:

Periodically, a slew of environmental laws has been enacted to address the severe environmental situation in the state. Prior to 1995, there was no such statute that comprehensively defined the term 'waste.' The Environmental Conservation Act of

⁷ <https://www.birlahospital.com/health-effects-of-plastic/>

⁸ <https://clearstone.co.uk/blogs/news/how-harmful-is-plastic-to-humans>

⁹ <https://www.ciel.org/project-update/plastic-and-human-health-a-lifecycle-approach-to-plastic-pollution/>

1995, however, provides a relatively explicit definition of "waste." However, Bangladesh lacks a comprehensive legislative framework for garbage management. However, Bangladesh has a number of local regulations addressing waste disposal. (Mohammad Jahid Mustofa, June 2020)¹⁰

1. Constitution of Bangladesh¹¹

The Bangladeshi constitution does not expressly address environmental degradation, but the constitutions of surrounding nations such as India, Malaysia, etc. contain specific environmental laws.

However, Part III of our Constitution incorporates a number of fundamental rights protections. Article 31 guarantees the right to life, which includes the right to live in an environment free of pollution.

In two decisions (Ain O Salish Kendra vs Bangladesh, 1999 BLD 488 and Prof. Nurul Islam V State, 2000, 52 DLR 413) where the 'right to life' was incorporated in the Constitution, the Supreme Court of Bangladesh rejected this argument. Included among the fundamental rights is the right to a healthy environment. (Mohammad Jahid Mustofa, June 2020).¹²

2. Environment Protection Act, 1995¹³

The Environment Protection Act of 1995 is the primary environmental protection statute in Bangladesh. Before establishing industrial projects, Section 12 of the 1995 Act stipulates that environmental considerations must be taken into account and environmental clearance must be obtained.

Section 16 of the Act stipulates a maximum sentence of ten years in prison or a maximum fine of 50,000/- taka.

The purpose of this law is to conserve, improve, control, and reduce environmental pollution across the entire spectrum of environmental dangers. However, a technical examination reveals that the law is not error-free.

¹⁰ https://seu.edu.bd/seujass/downloads/vol_03_issue_01_Jun_2020/SEUJASS-Vol03Issue01-5.pdf

¹¹ <http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-367.html>

¹² https://seu.edu.bd/seujass/downloads/vol_03_issue_01_Jun_2020/SEUJASS-Vol03Issue01-5.pdf

¹³ https://bangladeshbiosafety.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Bangladesh_Environmental_Conservation_Act_1995.pdf

3. Bangladesh Labor Act, 2006¹⁴

In accordance with Section 54 of the Bangladesh Labor Act of 2006, "effective measures shall be made for the disposal of rubbish and waste resulting from industrial operations in every institution." Section 351 stipulates that "the establishment shall make plans for the disposal of its wastes and waste, or get authorization from the prescribed authority for such arrangements."

4. The Ports Act, 1908¹⁵

"If any person willfully vitiates the atmosphere in any place so that it is injurious to the health of a person which could easily be done by improper discharge of waste, he shall be liable to a fine which may extend to five hundred taka" (Section 278, PC). Negligent handling of toxic substances and substance likely to explode shall be punishable under Sections 284 and 286. So, if the waste disposal is not done properly, the person can be punished under these sections.

According to Section 290, "Whoever causes a public nuisance in any case not otherwise punishable by this Code shall be liable to a fine which may extend to 200 taka. (Mohammad Jahid Mustofa, June 2020)¹⁶

5. The Jute Packaging Act 2010¹⁷

Section 14 of the Jute Packaging Act 2010 clearly states that if any person sells, distributes or supplies using synthetic wrappers without using jute wrappers, he shall be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding 1 year or with a fine not exceeding 50,000/- taka or both.

BELA Case References:

- **BLAST and BELA vs. Bangladesh and others [‘Water Logging’ Case]**

BLAST and Bangladesh Environmental Lawyers Association (BELA) filed a writ petition seeking orders to relieve the suffering caused to the people caused to the polluted environment resulting from frequent water logging and various wastes in those water bodies due to improper implementation. Residents of the region are

¹⁴ <http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-952.html>

¹⁵ <http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/act-89.html>

¹⁶ https://seu.edu.bd/seujass/downloads/vol_03_issue_01_Jun_2020/SEUJASS-Vol03Issue01-5.pdf

¹⁷ The bare act on the- ‘The Jute Packaging Act 2010’

forced to endure an inhumane life as their houses, farmlands, academic institutions and highways are flooded. Their biggest problem was overcrowding and creating an unhealthy environment in the water, even further obstructing it by pouring plastic debris into the water, which has resulted in horrific suffering among the people due to the constant failure and inaction of the authorities concerned. (Source: BLAST)¹⁸

Government Initiative:

Although Bangladesh has been implementing measures to reduce plastic pollution for years. Bangladesh was the first country in the world to prohibit plastic shopping bags in 2002. However, plastic pollution grew again after a few days. In 2020, a high court ordered the relevant authorities to prohibit the use of single-use plastics in all seaside hotels and motels across the nation.

In a report created in partnership with the Department of Environment and Pro Blue, a multi-donor trust fund, the short-term (2022-2023), the medium-term (2024-2026), and the long-term (2027-2028) were discussed (2027-2030). The initiative, which is tied to the Eighth Five-Year Plan, emphasizes the circular use of plastic based on the 3R strategy: reduce, reuse, and recycle.

The National Action Plan for Sustainable Plastics Management establishes a goal of 50 percent plastic recycling by 2025, a 90 percent single-use elimination objective by 2026, and a 30 percent reduction in plastic waste creation by 2030 compared to a baseline of 2020/21. We must encourage individuals to limit their plastic usage. (The Daily Star, 2022)¹⁹

Governments and individuals from all around the world are able to take meaningful steps to mitigate this environmental damage. Individuals can minimize their reliance on plastic by recycling some of the plastic products they consume. Many individuals carry water in glass bottles as opposed to disposable plastic ones. In this scenario, however, governments should do all possible to safeguard the environment from plastic garbage by enforcing a variety of rules and regulations at their discretion and continually organizing awareness campaigns.

¹⁸ <https://www.blast.org.bd/issues/223>

¹⁹ <https://www.thedailystar.net/environment/pollution/plastic-pollution/news/plastic-menace-worsening-2922001>

South Africa, for instance, has prohibited the production and use of plastic bags by legislative action. Additionally, governments might offer financial incentives to individuals and enterprises who do not utilize plastic products.

However, competent agencies and the general public can turn the tide and substantially remediate environmental harm. To accomplish this, they must ensure that both parties play their respective roles properly. First, individuals should voluntarily recycle plastic by placing plastic waste in a separate bin. The authorities must ensure that all plastics that are recyclable are recycled and recycled effectively. People should utilize bags produced from biodegradable materials such as jute fiber to reduce the use of plastic bags. They can begin carrying their glass water bottle instead of purchasing plastic ones. Reducing the consumption of plastic materials can have a significant impact on minimizing plastic's negative effects. Finally, the government can restrict the use of plastic bags and bottles by taxing them heavily.

Recommendation:

Plastic products are inexpensive, adaptable, and long-lasting, but they pose a threat to the environment. They contaminate soil and water, threaten animals, and serve as a breeding ground for lethal insects. There are numerous methods that authorities and communities can take to reduce the severity and scope of the problem.

Slowly, the situation is altering, and some businesses are implementing short-chain polymer molecules. Such compounds have significant potential in the building industry. Adding modest amounts of appropriately chosen polymers to conventional cement-based structural materials in Bangladesh could protect infrastructures in flood-prone areas, hence saving enormous amounts of money annually.

Bioplastics, which are plastic alternatives, are created solely from renewable biomass sources such as vegetable fats and oils, corn starch, cellulose, and lactic acid. (IOMC-Bioenergy and Bioresource: Open Access)²⁰ They can be produced from a mixture of agricultural waste and discarded plastic bottles and other containers, allowing for the modification of their qualities. The burning of plastic trash is a controversial but viable solution for plastic waste management. Given the limited land resources in Singapore, solid waste incineration is prioritized over all other waste transformation choices. They currently follow the waste-to-energy strategy well, decreasing the amount of waste discharged in landfills. Pyrolysis is an alternate approach that is gaining popularity in Bangladesh. It generates varying

²⁰ <https://www.iomcworld.org/medical-journals/bioplastics-48383.html>

quantities of potentially lucrative by-products from less hazardous compounds under optimal conditions. Afterwards, a number of research assessed the ability of conventional and innovative WWTP technologies to remove plastics using sophisticated wastewater technologies such as membranes, electrodeposition, and coagulation. Other novel tertiary treatment methods, such as fast gravity sand filters and dissolved air flotation, remove microplastics from primary and secondary effluents with removal rates of 95%. There are also more revolutionary technologies aimed at the elimination of various polymers.

Although research on the toxicological impacts of chemicals found in plastics is sparse, the hazard is genuine and present. The majority of remediation options are viable but costly. In a developing country such as Bangladesh, the viability of scaling is uncertain. Urgently implementing a policy for chemical exposure caused by plastic must be accompanied by research encouragement in the Global South. Developing more creative and recyclable plastic materials, as well as efficient recycling and wastewater treatment methods, must be thoroughly researched. The populace of Dhaka must be educated on the mechanics and severity of the situation, as well as the dangers of plastics to human health.

Conclusion:

Bangladesh banned polyethylene shopping bags first, but no real steps have been taken to eliminate plastic from the country. Inadequate waste management in Bangladesh is due to a lack of facilities, infrastructure development, and funds. A study explores the development and management of plastic waste in Bangladesh. Asia is the leading producer of plastic and waste.

According to UN Environment, humans produce 100 million tons of plastic waste annually. Solutions include recycling, reducing the use of plastic, and providing biodegradable substitutes. Each year, 8-10 million metric tons of plastic are dumped into the ocean. (The Conversation, February, 2015)²¹ Plastic waste is harmful to humans and marine life. Our carbon footprint is diminished when we use less plastic. This issue threatens the health of the oceans and the globe. Microplastic particles and hundreds of toxic compounds with carcinogenic, developmental, or endocrine-disrupting properties are released by plastics. Inflammation, genotoxicity, oxidative stress, apoptosis, and necrosis can be caused by microplastics.

The incompetence and inaction of authorities to tackle flooding are causing unimaginable agony. The Supreme Court of Bangladesh ordered the government to establish a 90-day plan to phase out pesticides containing glyphosate, such as Roundup. Governments should enact regulations to safeguard the environment from plastic waste. South Africa prohibits the use of plastic bags. Reducing plastic consumption can lessen its negative effects.

²¹ <https://www.rawstory.com/2015/02/eight-million-tons-of-plastic-are-dumped-into-the-ocean-each-year-study-finds/>

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